

**FINITE SEARCHES, CHOWLA'S COSINE PROBLEM, AND
LARGE NEWMAN POLYNOMIALS**

Idris Mercer

*Department of Mathematics and Statistics, Florida International University,
Miami, Florida
imercer@fiu.edu*

Received: 8/17/17, Revised: 5/3/18, Accepted: 12/19/18, Published: 1/5/19

Abstract

A length n cosine sum is an expression of the form $\cos a_1\theta + \cdots + \cos a_n\theta$ where $a_1 < \cdots < a_n$ are positive integers, and a length n Newman polynomial is an expression of the form $z^{a_1} + \cdots + z^{a_n}$ where $a_1 < \cdots < a_n$ are nonnegative integers. We define $-\lambda(n)$ to be the largest minimum of a length n cosine sum as $\{a_1, \dots, a_n\}$ ranges over all sets of n positive integers, and we define $\mu(n)$ to be the largest minimum modulus on the unit circle of a length n Newman polynomial as $\{a_1, \dots, a_n\}$ ranges over all sets of n nonnegative integers. Since there are infinitely many possibilities for the a_j , it is not obvious how to compute $\lambda(n)$ or $\mu(n)$ for a given n in finitely many steps. Campbell et al. found the value of $\mu(3)$ in 1983, and Goddard found the value of $\mu(4)$ in 1992. In this paper, we find the values of $\lambda(2)$ and $\lambda(3)$ and nontrivial bounds on $\mu(5)$. We also include further remarks on the seemingly difficult general task of reducing the computation of $\lambda(n)$ or $\mu(n)$ to a finite problem.

1. Introduction

We define a *length n cosine sum* to be any expression of the form

$$\cos a_1\theta + \cdots + \cos a_n\theta$$

where $a_1 < \cdots < a_n$ are positive integers. If $f(\theta)$ is a length n cosine sum, then $f(0) = n$ and $f(\theta) \geq -n$ for all θ . For $f(\theta) = \cos a_1\theta + \cdots + \cos a_n\theta$, we define

$$L(a_1, \dots, a_n) = \min_{\theta} f(\theta) = \min_{0 \leq \theta \leq \pi} f(\theta)$$

which is negative, since $f(\theta)$ has average value 0 on $[0, \pi]$. More specifically, we have

$$-n \leq L(a_1, \dots, a_n) < 0.$$

We then define

$$-\lambda(n) = \sup L(a_1, \dots, a_n)$$

where $\{a_1, \dots, a_n\}$ ranges over all of the infinitely many sets of n positive integers. Then $0 \leq \lambda(n) \leq n$. There is also a construction showing $\lambda(n) = O(\sqrt{n})$ (see Section 2).

We define a *length n Newman polynomial* to be any expression of the form

$$z^{a_1} + \dots + z^{a_n}$$

where $a_1 < \dots < a_n$ are nonnegative integers. If $F(z)$ is a length n Newman polynomial and $|z| = 1$, then $0 \leq |F(z)| \leq n$. We define

$$M(a_1, \dots, a_n) = \min_{|z|=1} |z^{a_1} + \dots + z^{a_n}|$$

so we have

$$0 \leq M(a_1, \dots, a_n) \leq n,$$

and in fact one can show $M(a_1, \dots, a_n) \leq \sqrt{n}$ by considering the L^2 norm of F . (We note that the case $n = 2$ is uninteresting because $z^{a_1} + z^{a_2} = z^{a_1}(1 + z^{a_2-a_1})$ always has minimum modulus 0 at the $(a_2 - a_1)$ th roots of -1 .) We then define

$$\mu(n) = \sup M(a_1, \dots, a_n)$$

where $\{a_1, \dots, a_n\}$ ranges over all of the infinitely many sets of n nonnegative integers.

Then $\lambda(n)$ and $\mu(n)$ are well-defined functions of n because we are taking the supremum of a bounded set. However, since there are infinitely many possibilities for the a_j , it is not obvious how to compute $\lambda(n)$ or $\mu(n)$ for a given n in finitely many steps. Also, since $\lambda(n)$ and $\mu(n)$ are defined as suprema of infinite sets, it is not obvious if $\lambda(n)$ or $\mu(n)$ are always equal to $-L(a_1, \dots, a_n)$ or $M(a_1, \dots, a_n)$ for a specific choice of a_1, \dots, a_n . In any case, some brute-force exploration of specific small examples leads to conjectures such as

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda(2) &= -L(1, 2) = 9/8 = 1.125, \\ \lambda(3) &= -L(1, 2, 3) \approx 1.315565, \\ \lambda(4) &= -L(1, 2, 3, 4) \approx 1.519558, \\ \lambda(5) &= -L(1, 2, 4, 5, 6) \approx 1.627461, \\ \lambda(6) &= -L(1, 2, 4, 6, 7, 8) \approx 1.591832, \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \mu(3) &= M(0, 1, 3) \approx 0.607346, \\ \mu(4) &= M(0, 1, 2, 4) \approx 0.752394, \\ \mu(5) &= M(0, 1, 2, 6, 9) = 1. \end{aligned}$$

In 1983, Campbell et al. [2] proved that $\mu(3) = M(0, 1, 3)$, and in 1992, Goddard [6] proved that $\mu(4) = M(0, 1, 2, 4)$. To prove results of that type, one must reduce a potentially infinite search to a finite search. The main results of this paper are:

Theorem 1.1. *We have*

$$\lambda(2) = -L(1, 2) = 9/8 = 1.125,$$

$$\lambda(3) = -L(1, 2, 3) = \frac{17 + 7\sqrt{7}}{27} \approx 1.315565.$$

Theorem 1.2. *We have $1 \leq \mu(5) \leq 1 + \pi/6 \approx 1.5236$.*

Theorem 1.1 is proved in Section 4 and Theorem 1.2 is proved in Section 6.

Various authors have investigated the growth rates of the functions $\lambda(n)$ and $\mu(n)$. Around the late 1940s, Ankeny and Chowla conjectured [3, 4] that $\lambda(n)$ approaches infinity with n . This was first proved by Uchiyama and Uchiyama [9] using results of Cohen [5]; their lower bound for $\lambda(n)$ was sublogarithmic. Over the years, better lower bounds for $\lambda(n)$ have been found. The best lower bound currently known is due to Ruzsa [8]; it is superlogarithmic but grows more slowly than any power of n . The best known upper bound for $\lambda(n)$ appears to be $O(\sqrt{n})$. Chowla conjectured [4] that this is the true rate of growth.

It seems that the growth of $\mu(n)$ is less studied than the growth of $\lambda(n)$. There is a construction showing $\mu(n)$ exceeds a power of n for infinitely many n ; specifically, we have $\mu(n) \geq n^{0.14}$ when n is a power of 9 (See Section 2). Boyd [1] conjectured that $\mu(n) > 1$ for all $n \geq 6$ and that $\log \mu(n)/\log n$ approaches a positive constant as n approaches infinity. The current author [7] proved that $\mu(n) > 0$ for all $n > 2$. It appears that nobody has proved that $\mu(n)$ approaches infinity with n .

It would be interesting to show that for any n , the value of $\lambda(n)$ or $\mu(n)$ can be computed in a finite number of steps (even an impractically large finite number) and it would be interesting to know if $\lambda(n)$ and $\mu(n)$ are always equal to $-L(a_1, \dots, a_n)$ or $M(a_1, \dots, a_n)$ for a specific choice of the a_j . This appears to be difficult to prove.

2. Constructions Bounding $\lambda(n)$ and $\mu(n)$

There are some straightforward constructions that lead to bounds on $\lambda(n)$ and $\mu(n)$. These probably count as mathematical folklore. We include them here for completeness.

Lemma 2.1. *For each positive integer n , there exists a length n cosine sum $f(\theta)$ that satisfies $f(\theta) \geq -\sqrt{2n} - \frac{1}{2}$ for all θ . It follows that $\lambda(n) \leq \sqrt{2n} + \frac{1}{2}$.*

Proof. Let $k = \lceil \sqrt{2n} \rceil$, so $\sqrt{2n} \leq k < \sqrt{2n} + 1$. Let $\{b_1 < \dots < b_k\}$ be a set of k nonnegative integers such that the $\binom{k}{2}$ positive differences $b_j - b_i$ are all distinct;

for instance, we can take $b_j = 2^{j-1}$. (A set with this property is sometimes called a ‘Sidon set’; in this proof, we do not need our Sidon set to be optimal in any sense.) Then if $z = e^{i\theta}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} 0 \leq |z^{b_1} + \dots + z^{b_k}|^2 &= (z^{b_1} + \dots + z^{b_k})(z^{-b_1} + \dots + z^{-b_k}) \\ &= k + \sum_{i < j} 2\operatorname{Re}(z^{b_j - b_i}) = k + 2 \sum_{i < j} \cos(b_j - b_i)\theta. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, if we define $g(\theta) = \sum_{i < j} \cos(b_j - b_i)\theta$, then $g(\theta)$ is a length $\binom{k}{2}$ cosine sum satisfying $g(\theta) \geq -k/2$ for all θ . Now observe

$$n - \sqrt{\frac{n}{2}} = \frac{\sqrt{2n}(\sqrt{2n} - 1)}{2} \leq \frac{k(k-1)}{2} < \frac{(\sqrt{2n} + 1)\sqrt{2n}}{2} = n + \sqrt{\frac{n}{2}}.$$

If $\binom{k}{2} > n$, choose $h(\theta)$ to be a sum consisting of $\binom{k}{2} - n$ of the cosines in the sum $g(\theta)$, and choose $f(\theta) = g(\theta) - h(\theta)$. If $\binom{k}{2} < n$, choose $h(\theta)$ to be a sum of $n - \binom{k}{2}$ cosines not appearing in the sum $g(\theta)$, and choose $f(\theta) = g(\theta) + h(\theta)$. If $\binom{k}{2} = n$, define $h(\theta) = 0$ and choose $f(\theta) = g(\theta)$.

Then $h(\theta)$ is a sum of at most $\sqrt{n/2}$ cosines, so we have $\pm h(\theta) \geq -\sqrt{n/2}$. We then have

$$f(\theta) = g(\theta) \pm h(\theta) \geq -\frac{k}{2} - \sqrt{\frac{n}{2}} > -\frac{\sqrt{2n} + 1}{2} - \sqrt{\frac{n}{2}} = -\sqrt{2n} - \frac{1}{2}$$

which completes the proof. □

Lemma 2.2. *Let F be a length n Newman polynomial satisfying $|F(z)| \geq K_1$ for all $|z| = 1$, and let G be a length m Newman polynomial satisfying $|G(z)| \geq K_2$ for all $|z| = 1$. Then there exists a length nm Newman polynomial H satisfying $|H(z)| \geq K_1K_2$ for all $|z| = 1$.*

Proof. Suppose

$$\begin{aligned} F(z) &= z^{a_1} + \dots + z^{a_n}, \\ G(z) &= z^{b_1} + \dots + z^{b_m}. \end{aligned}$$

If k is a sufficiently large positive integer, then the product

$$H(z) = F(z^k)G(z) = (z^{ka_1} + \dots + z^{ka_n})(z^{b_1} + \dots + z^{b_m})$$

has the property that the nm exponents $ka_i + b_j$ are all distinct, and hence $H(z)$ is a Newman polynomial of length nm . If $|z| = 1$, then $|H(z)| = |F(z^k)| |G(z)| \geq K_1K_2$. This completes the proof. □

As mentioned in [1], the length 9 Newman polynomial

$$F(z) = 1 + z + z^2 + z^3 + z^4 + z^7 + z^8 + z^{10} + z^{12}$$

has unusually high minimum modulus on the unit circle. Specifically, $|F(z)| \geq 1.362$ for all z on the unit circle. Then, by repeated application of Lemma 2.2, we can construct for each k a Newman polynomial $H(z)$ of length 9^k with the property that $|H(z)| \geq 1.362^k$ for all z on the unit circle. Since $1.362 > 9^{0.14}$, this means that for infinitely many values of n , we have a length n Newman polynomial $H(z)$ that satisfies $|H(z)| \geq n^{0.14}$ on the unit circle.

For example, there is a Newman polynomial of length $9^3 = 729$ that satisfies $|H(z)| \geq 1.362^3 \approx 2.53$ on the unit circle, so $\mu(729) \geq 2.53$. It would be interesting to know (for example) the least n such that $\mu(n) \geq 2$.

3. Some Notation and Lemmas

In this section, we establish some notation and some useful lemmas.

Let $f(\theta) = \cos a_1\theta + \dots + \cos a_n\theta$, let $g = \gcd(a_1, \dots, a_n)$, and let $a'_j = a_j/g$. Then $\cos a'_1\theta + \dots + \cos a'_n\theta$ is a length n cosine sum taking on the same values (and hence having the same minimum) as $f(\theta)$. Therefore, in the definition of $\lambda(n)$, it suffices to consider only those $\{a_1, \dots, a_n\}$ for which $\gcd(a_1, \dots, a_n) = 1$.

Let $F(z) = z^{a_1} + \dots + z^{a_n}$, where $a_1 < \dots < a_n$ are nonnegative integers. Define $b_j = a_j - a_1$. If $|z| = 1$, then

$$F_1(z) = F(z)/z^{a_1} = 1 + z^{b_2} + \dots + z^{b_n}$$

has the same modulus as $F(z)$. Next, define $g = \gcd(b_2, \dots, b_n)$ and $b'_j = b_j/g$. If

$$F_2(z) = 1 + z^{b'_2} + \dots + z^{b'_n}$$

then $F_2(z^g) = F_1(z)$, so $F_1(z)$ and $F_2(z)$ have the same set of outputs as z ranges over the unit circle. Therefore, in the definition of $\mu(n)$, it suffices to consider only those $\{a_1, \dots, a_n\}$ of the form $\{0, a_2, \dots, a_n\}$ where $\gcd(a_2, \dots, a_n) = 1$. Furthermore, there is one more symmetry we exploit. If

$$F(z) = 1 + z^{a_2} + \dots + z^{a_{n-1}} + z^{a_n}$$

then we define

$$H(z) = z^{a_n} F(z^{-1}) = z^{a_n} + z^{a_n - a_2} + \dots + z^{a_n - a_{n-1}} + 1,$$

and note that $|F(z)|$ and $|H(z)|$ have the same set of outputs as z ranges over the unit circle. So we are free to choose between $F(z)$ and $H(z)$ and can hence assume $a_{n-1} \geq a_n - a_2$.

For the above reasons, we make the following definitions. Define

$$\mathbb{N}'_n = \{(a_1, \dots, a_n) \mid 0 < a_1 < \dots < a_n, \gcd(a_1, \dots, a_n) = 1\},$$

$$\mathbb{N}''_n = \{(0, a_2, \dots, a_n) \mid 0 < a_2 < \dots < a_n, \gcd(a_2, \dots, a_n) = 1, a_{n-1} \geq a_n - a_2\}$$

and note that if $L(a_1, \dots, a_n)$ and $M(a_1, \dots, a_n)$ are as defined in Section 1, then we have

$$-\lambda(n) = \sup L(a_1, \dots, a_n)$$

where the supremum is taken over all $(a_1, \dots, a_n) \in \mathbb{N}'_n$, and we have

$$\mu(n) = \sup M(0, a_2, \dots, a_n)$$

where the supremum is taken over all $(0, a_2, \dots, a_n) \in \mathbb{N}''_n$.

We also define \mathbb{T} to be $\mathbb{R} \bmod 2\pi$. Following are some definitions and lemmas regarding subsets of \mathbb{T} .

Definition. An *equispaced subset* of \mathbb{T} of order m is any subset of \mathbb{T} of the form

$$\left\{ \theta_0 + \frac{2k\pi}{m} \mid k \in \mathbb{Z} \right\}.$$

Note that if we fix $\xi \in \mathbb{T}$, then the set $\{\theta \in \mathbb{T} \mid m\theta = \xi\}$ is an equispaced set of order m .

Lemma 3.1. *Let S_1 and S_2 be equispaced subsets of \mathbb{T} of order m_1 and m_2 respectively, and let $g = \gcd(m_1, m_2)$. Then there exists $\theta_1 \in S_1$ and $\theta_2 \in S_2$ such that $|\theta_1 - \theta_2| \leq \frac{\pi g}{m_1 m_2}$.*

Proof. Suppose

$$S_1 = \left\{ \xi_1 + \frac{2k\pi}{m_1} \mid k \in \mathbb{Z} \right\} \quad \text{and} \quad S_2 = \left\{ \xi_2 + \frac{2k\pi}{m_2} \mid k \in \mathbb{Z} \right\}.$$

The real number $\frac{m_1 m_2}{2\pi}(\xi_1 - \xi_2)$ must be within $\frac{g}{2}$ of an integer multiple of g , call it ag . Also, ag can be written in the form $km_1 - \ell m_2$ for some integers k and ℓ . Thus we have

$$\left| \frac{m_1 m_2}{2\pi}(\xi_1 - \xi_2) - (km_1 - \ell m_2) \right| \leq \frac{g}{2},$$

which, multiplying by $\frac{2\pi}{m_1 m_2}$ and rearranging, gives us

$$\left| \left(\xi_1 + \frac{2\pi\ell}{m_1} \right) - \left(\xi_2 + \frac{2\pi k}{m_2} \right) \right| \leq \frac{\pi g}{m_1 m_2},$$

completing the proof of the lemma. □

The following lemma is straightforward.

Lemma 3.2. *If θ satisfies $|\theta - \pi| = \varepsilon$, then $\cos \theta \leq -1 + \frac{1}{2}\varepsilon^2$.*

We will also need other bounds on the cosine function, which need not be the best bounds possible. One can show the following.

Lemma 3.3. *If θ satisfies $|\theta - \frac{2\pi}{3}| = \varepsilon \leq \frac{\pi}{6}$, then*

$$\cos \theta \leq -\frac{1}{2} + \frac{3}{\pi}\varepsilon$$

and if θ satisfies $|\theta - \frac{4\pi}{3}| = \varepsilon \leq \frac{\pi}{6}$, then

$$\cos \theta \leq -\frac{1}{2} + \frac{3}{\pi}\varepsilon.$$

Definition. If $S \subset \mathbb{T}$ is an equispaced set of order m , and $f(\theta)$ and $g(\theta)$ are real-valued functions on \mathbb{T} , then we define

$$\langle f(\theta), g(\theta) \rangle_S = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{\theta \in S} f(\theta)g(\theta),$$

the average value of $f(\theta)g(\theta)$ over S , which we can think of as a kind of dot product of $f(\theta)$ and $g(\theta)$.

One can verify that this dot product has the following properties:

- $\langle f_1(\theta) + f_2(\theta), g(\theta) \rangle_S = \langle f_1(\theta), g(\theta) \rangle_S + \langle f_2(\theta), g(\theta) \rangle_S$
- $\langle f(\theta), g_1(\theta) + g_2(\theta) \rangle_S = \langle f(\theta), g_1(\theta) \rangle_S + \langle f(\theta), g_2(\theta) \rangle_S$
- $\langle 1, 1 \rangle_S = 1$
- $\langle 1, \cos k\theta \rangle_S = \langle \cos k\theta, 1 \rangle_S = 0$ if k is *not* a multiple of m
- $\langle \cos k\theta, \cos k\theta \rangle_S = \frac{1}{2}$ if $2k$ is *not* a multiple of m
- $\langle \cos k\theta, \cos \ell\theta \rangle_S = 0$ if $k + \ell$ and $k - \ell$ are *not* multiples of m

A function that is nonnegative on \mathbb{T} can be used as a ‘weight function’. Some examples of nonnegative weight functions are:

$$1 - \cos k\theta,$$

$$2(1 - \cos k\theta)^2 = 3 - 4 \cos k\theta + \cos 2k\theta,$$

as well as any sum of such functions.

Lemma 3.4. *Let $w(\theta)$ be a nonnegative weight function on \mathbb{T} , let $g(\theta)$ be any real-valued function on \mathbb{T} , and let $S \subset \mathbb{T}$ be an equispaced set. If we have $\langle w(\theta), g(\theta) \rangle_S \leq 0$, then $g(\theta) \leq 0$ for some $\theta \in \mathbb{T}$.*

4. The Values of $\lambda(2)$ and $\lambda(3)$

To prove $\lambda(2) = -L(1, 2) = 9/8$, let $(a, b) \in \mathbb{N}'_2$, so $\gcd(a, b) = 1$. We must show that $\cos a\theta + \cos b\theta \leq -9/8$ for some θ .

If $b \leq 2$, then $\cos a\theta + \cos b\theta = \cos \theta + \cos 2\theta$, which one can verify has minimum value $-9/8$. So suppose $b \geq 3$. Define

$$S_1 = \{\theta \in \mathbb{T} \mid a\theta = \pi\} \quad \text{and} \quad S_2 = \{\theta \in \mathbb{T} \mid b\theta = \pi\},$$

which are equispaced sets of order a and b respectively. By Lemma 3.1, there exist $\theta_1 \in S_1$ and $\theta_2 \in S_2$ such that $|\theta_1 - \theta_2| \leq \frac{\pi}{ab}$. Then $\cos b\theta_2 = \pi$ and $|a\theta_2 - \pi| = |a\theta_2 - a\theta_1| \leq \frac{\pi}{b}$, so by Lemma 3.2, we have

$$\cos a\theta_2 \leq -1 + \frac{\pi^2}{2b^2} \leq -1 + \frac{\pi^2}{18} \approx -0.45,$$

implying $\cos a\theta_2 + \cos b\theta_2 \leq -2 + \frac{\pi^2}{18} \approx -1.45 < -9/8$. This completes the evaluation of $\lambda(2)$.

Next, we will show that $\lambda(3) = -L(1, 2, 3)$. First, observe that trigonometric identities allow us to write

$$\begin{aligned} \cos \theta + \cos 2\theta + \cos 3\theta &= \cos \theta + (2 \cos^2 \theta - 1) + (4 \cos^3 \theta - 3 \cos \theta) \\ &= 4 \cos^3 \theta + 2 \cos^2 \theta - 2 \cos \theta - 1 \end{aligned}$$

which is a polynomial in $\cos \theta$ of degree 3. One can verify that

$$\min_{-1 \leq c \leq 1} 4c^3 + 2c^2 - 2c - 1 = -\frac{17 + 7\sqrt{7}}{27} \approx -1.315565.$$

That is, $-L(1, 2, 3) = \frac{17+7\sqrt{7}}{27} \approx 1.315565$. For brevity, let $K = -L(1, 2, 3)$.

To prove that $\lambda(3) = K$, we will partition \mathbb{N}'_3 into four subsets:

$$\begin{aligned} M_1 &= \{(a, b, c) \in \mathbb{N}'_3 \mid c = 2a\}, \\ M_2 &= \{(a, b, c) \in \mathbb{N}'_3 \mid c = 2b\}, \\ M_3 &= \{(a, b, c) \in \mathbb{N}'_3 \mid c = a + b\}, \\ M_0 &= \{(a, b, c) \in \mathbb{N}'_3 \mid c \notin \{2a, 2b, a + b\}\}. \end{aligned}$$

Speaking very informally, we can think of M_1, M_2, M_3 as subsets of \mathbb{N}'_3 that have only two ‘degrees of freedom’. For each $j \in \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$, we will show that with finitely many exceptions, if $(a, b, c) \in M_j$ then $\cos a\theta + \cos b\theta + \cos c\theta \leq -K$ for some θ .

Suppose $(a, b, c) \in M_0$. We then have $0 < a < b < c$, $\gcd(a, b, c) = 1$, and $c \notin \{2a, 2b, a + b\}$. Let $S = \{\theta \in \mathbb{T} \mid c\theta = \pi\}$, which is an equispaced set of order c . Note that $2 - \cos a\theta - \cos b\theta$ is a nonnegative weight function, and consider

$$\delta = \left\langle 2 - \cos a\theta - \cos b\theta, \frac{1}{2} + \cos a\theta + \cos b\theta \right\rangle_S.$$

Now observe that none of a , b , or $b - a$ is a multiple of c , and that any of $2a$, $2b$, or $a + b$ that is a multiple of c must equal c . It then follows from properties of the dot product that

$$\delta = \left\langle 2, \frac{1}{2} \right\rangle_S - \langle \cos a\theta, \cos a\theta \rangle_S - \langle \cos b\theta, \cos b\theta \rangle_S = 1 - \frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{2} = 0$$

and then by Lemma 3.4, we conclude that $\frac{1}{2} + \cos a\theta + \cos b\theta \leq 0$ for some $\theta \in S$. But that θ satisfies $\cos c\theta = -1$ and therefore $\cos a\theta + \cos b\theta + \cos c\theta \leq -3/2 < -K$.

Next, suppose $(a, b, c) \in M_1$. If $a \leq 2$ then (a, b, c) must be $(2, 3, 4)$, and we observe that $\cos 2\theta + \cos 3\theta + \cos 4\theta = -2 < -K$ if $\theta = \pi/3$. We therefore assume $a \geq 3$. Now define

$$S_1 = \left\{ \theta \in \mathbb{T} \mid a\theta = \frac{2\pi}{3} \right\}, \quad S_2 = \{ \theta \in \mathbb{T} \mid b\theta = \pi \},$$

which are equispaced sets of order a and b respectively. Note that $\gcd(a, b) = 1$ since any common divisor would divide $2a = c$. By Lemma 3.1, there exist $\theta_1 \in S_1$ and $\theta_2 \in S_2$ such that $|\theta_1 - \theta_2| \leq \frac{\pi}{ab}$. Then $\cos a\theta_1 = \cos 2\pi/3 = -1/2$ and $\cos c\theta_1 = \cos 2a\theta_1 = \cos 4\pi/3 = -1/2$. Also, we have $|b\theta_1 - \pi| = |b\theta_1 - b\theta_2| \leq \frac{\pi}{a}$, so by Lemma 3.2, we have

$$\cos b\theta_1 \leq -1 + \frac{\pi^2}{2a^2} \leq -1 + \frac{\pi^2}{18} \approx -0.45,$$

implying $\cos a\theta_1 + \cos b\theta_1 + \cos c\theta_1 \leq -2 + \frac{\pi^2}{18} \approx -1.45 < -K$.

Next, suppose $(a, b, c) \in M_2$. This case is very similar to $(a, b, c) \in M_1$. If $b \leq 2$ then (a, b, c) must be $(1, 2, 4)$, and we observe that $\cos \theta + \cos 2\theta + \cos 4\theta = -3/2 < -K$ if $\theta = 2\pi/3$. We therefore assume $b \geq 3$. We define

$$S_1 = \{ \theta \in \mathbb{T} \mid a\theta = \pi \}, \quad S_2 = \left\{ \theta \in \mathbb{T} \mid b\theta = \frac{2\pi}{3} \right\},$$

which are equispaced sets of order a and b , and we note that $\gcd(a, b) = 1$, so there exist $\theta_1 \in S_1$ and $\theta_2 \in S_2$ such that $|\theta_1 - \theta_2| \leq \frac{\pi}{ab}$. Then $\cos b\theta_2 = \cos 2\pi/3 = -1/2$ and $\cos c\theta_2 = \cos 2b\theta_2 = \cos 4\pi/3 = -1/2$. Also, we have $|a\theta_2 - \pi| = |a\theta_2 - a\theta_1| \leq \frac{\pi}{b}$, so Lemma 3.2 gives us

$$\cos a\theta_2 \leq -1 + \frac{\pi^2}{2b^2} \leq -1 + \frac{\pi^2}{18} \approx -0.45,$$

implying $\cos a\theta_2 + \cos b\theta_2 + \cos c\theta_2 \leq -2 + \frac{\pi^2}{18} \approx -1.45 < -K$.

Finally, suppose $(a, b, c) \in M_3$. We will show the existence of a finite subset $M' \subset M_3$ such that if $(a, b, c) \in M_3 \setminus M'$, then $\cos a\theta + \cos b\theta + \cos c\theta \leq -K$ for some θ . That will reduce this case to checking the finitely many elements of M' . It will suffice to choose

$$M' = \{ (a, b, c) \in M_3 \mid b \leq 32 \} = \{ (a, b, a + b) \in M_3 \mid 1 \leq a < b \leq 32 \}$$

which has at most $\binom{32}{2} = 496$ elements. At the end of this section, we will give an alternative argument that avoids such a large finite set.

So suppose $(a, b, c) \in M_3 \setminus M'$, so $c = a + b$ and $b \geq 33$. We choose

$$S_1 = \left\{ \theta \in \mathbb{T} \mid a\theta = \frac{2\pi}{3} \right\}, \quad S_2 = \left\{ \theta \in \mathbb{T} \mid b\theta = \frac{2\pi}{3} \right\},$$

which are equispaced sets of order a and b respectively. Note that $\gcd(a, b) = 1$ since any common divisor would divide $a+b = c$. By Lemma 3.1, there exist $\theta_1 \in S_1$ and $\theta_2 \in S_2$ such that $|\theta_1 - \theta_2| \leq \frac{\pi}{ab}$. Then $\cos b\theta_2 = \cos 2\pi/3 = -1/2$. Also, we have $|a\theta_2 - 2\pi/3| = |a\theta_2 - a\theta_1| \leq \frac{\pi}{b}$ and

$$\left| c\theta_2 - \frac{4\pi}{3} \right| = \left| \left(a\theta_2 - \frac{2\pi}{3} \right) + \left(b\theta_2 - \frac{2\pi}{3} \right) \right| = \left| \left(a\theta_2 - \frac{2\pi}{3} \right) + 0 \right| \leq \frac{\pi}{b}.$$

By Lemma 3.3, we then have

$$\cos a\theta_2 \leq -\frac{1}{2} + \frac{3\pi}{\pi b} \quad \text{and} \quad \cos c\theta_2 \leq -\frac{1}{2} + \frac{3\pi}{\pi b}$$

which implies

$$\cos a\theta_2 + \cos b\theta_2 + \cos c\theta_2 \leq -\frac{3}{2} + \frac{6}{b} \leq -\frac{3}{2} + \frac{6}{33} \approx -1.318 < -K.$$

We remark that the case $(a, b, c) \in M_3$ can be dealt with more easily if we take as known the fact that

$$\mu(3) = M(0, 1, 3) = \sqrt{\frac{47 - 14\sqrt{7}}{27}} \approx 0.607346,$$

which was shown in Section 3 of [2]. Note that this result says that given any degree 3 Newman polynomial $F(z) = 1 + z^k + z^\ell$, we have $|F(z)| \leq M(0, 1, 3)$ for some $|z| = 1$. We apply this to the case $F(z) = 1 + z^a + z^{a+b}$. The statement

$$|1 + z^a + z^{a+b}| \leq \sqrt{\frac{47 - 14\sqrt{7}}{27}} \quad \text{for some } |z| = 1$$

is equivalent to

$$|1 + z^a + z^{a+b}|^2 \leq \frac{47 - 14\sqrt{7}}{27} \quad \text{for some } |z| = 1$$

but we also have, if $z = e^{i\theta}$,

$$\begin{aligned} |1 + z^a + z^{a+b}|^2 &= (1 + z^a + z^{a+b})(1 + z^{-a} + z^{-a-b}) \\ &= 3 + (z^a + z^{-a}) + (z^b + z^{-b}) + (z^{a+b} + z^{-a-b}) \\ &= 3 + 2(\cos a\theta + \cos b\theta + \cos(a+b)\theta). \end{aligned}$$

The condition

$$3 + 2(\cos a\theta + \cos b\theta + \cos(a + b)\theta) \leq \frac{47 - 14\sqrt{7}}{27}$$

is equivalent to

$$\cos a\theta + \cos b\theta + \cos(a + b)\theta \leq \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{47 - 14\sqrt{7}}{27} - 3 \right) = -\frac{17 + 7\sqrt{7}}{27} = L(1, 2, 3).$$

In [2], the fact that $\mu(3) = M(0, 1, 3)$ is proved by reducing to a finite number of cases, but their number of cases is much less than 496. Since we used the value of $\mu(3)$ just in the case where $(a, b, c) \in M_3$, it could be said that our evaluation of $\lambda(3)$ is a generalization of the evaluation of $\mu(3)$.

5. A Possible Strategy for $\lambda(4)$

The current author is unaware of how to evaluate $\lambda(4)$, but includes in this section a possible outline of a strategy where we reduce that problem to a finite set of problems that, speaking informally, have fewer ‘degrees of freedom’.

We conjecture that $\lambda(4) = -L(1, 2, 3, 4) \approx 1.519558$. To prove this, we must show that if $(a, b, c, d) \in \mathbb{N}'_4$, then $\cos a\theta + \cos b\theta + \cos c\theta + \cos d\theta \leq L(1, 2, 3, 4)$ for some θ .

Let $(a, b, c, d) \in \mathbb{N}'_4$, and define $S = \{\theta \in \mathbb{T} \mid d\theta = \pi\}$, which is an equispaced set of order d . Define the nonnegative weight function

$$\begin{aligned} w(\theta) &= (1 - \cos a\theta) + (1 - \cos b\theta) + 2(1 - \cos c\theta)^2 \\ &= 1 - \cos a\theta + 1 - \cos b\theta + 3 - 4 \cos c\theta + \cos 2c\theta \\ &= 5 - \cos a\theta - \cos b\theta - 4 \cos c\theta + \cos 2c\theta. \end{aligned}$$

If we can show that

$$\left\langle w(\theta), \frac{3}{5} + \cos a\theta + \cos b\theta + \cos c\theta \right\rangle_S \leq 0,$$

then it will follow that $\cos a\theta + \cos b\theta + \cos c\theta \leq -3/5$ for some θ satisfying $\cos d\theta = -1$, so then $\cos a\theta + \cos b\theta + \cos c\theta + \cos d\theta \leq -8/5 = -1.6 < L(1, 2, 3, 4)$.

Using previously stated properties of the dot product, we note that evaluating

$$\left\langle 5 - \cos a\theta - \cos b\theta - 4 \cos c\theta + \cos 2c\theta, \frac{3}{5} + \cos a\theta + \cos b\theta + \cos c\theta \right\rangle_S$$

depends on properties of the set $\{0, a, b, c, 2c\} \pm \{0, a, b, c\}$. This is illustrated in Table 1. If all the nonzero numbers in the body of Table 1 are nonmultiples of d ,

	0	a	b	c	$2c$
0	0	a	b	c	$2c$
a	a	$2a$	$b \pm a$	$c \pm a$	$2c \pm a$
b	b	$b \pm a$	$2b$	$c \pm b$	$2c \pm b$
c	c	$c \pm a$	$c \pm b$	$2c$	$2c \pm c$

Table 1: Elements of $\{0, a, b, c, 2c\} \pm \{0, a, b, c\}$

then properties of the dot product give us

$$\begin{aligned} & \left\langle 5 - \cos a\theta - \cos b\theta - 4 \cos c\theta + \cos 2c\theta, \frac{3}{5} + \cos a\theta + \cos b\theta + \cos c\theta \right\rangle_S \\ &= 5 \cdot \frac{3}{5} - \frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{2} - 4 \cdot \frac{1}{2} = 0 \end{aligned}$$

and so in that case, the desired conclusion follows. We now observe:

- The positive numbers $a, b, c, b - a, c - a, c - b$ are all less than d , and are hence nonmultiples of d .
- The positive numbers $2a, 2b, 2c, b + a, c + a, c + b, 2c - a, 2c - b$ are all less than $2d$, and hence if any of them are multiples of d , they are equal to d .
- The positive numbers $2c + a, 2c + b, 2c + c$ are all less than $3d$, and hence if any of them are multiples of d , they are equal to d or $2d$.

It follows that if $(a, b, c, d) \in \mathbb{N}'_4$ has the property that d is *not* equal to any of these 14 linear combinations of a, b, c

$$2a, 2b, 2c, b + a, c + a, c + b, 2c - a, 2c - b, 2c + a, c + \frac{1}{2}a, 2c + b, c + \frac{1}{2}b, 3c, \frac{3}{2}c$$

then $\cos a\theta + \cos b\theta + \cos c\theta + \cos d\theta \leq -8/5 < L(1, 2, 3, 4)$ for some θ . It then remains to deal with those (a, b, c, d) where d is equal to one of the 14 combinations listed above.

Enumerate those 14 linear combinations as $\varphi_1(a, b, c), \dots, \varphi_{14}(a, b, c)$, and then for $1 \leq j \leq 14$, define

$$M_j = \{(a, b, c, d) \in \mathbb{N}'_4 \mid d = \varphi_j(a, b, c)\}.$$

Then each M_j , speaking very informally, is a subset of \mathbb{N}'_4 having only 3 ‘degrees of freedom’. If we can prove for each j that if $(a, b, c, d) \in M_j$, then $\cos a\theta + \cos b\theta + \cos c\theta + \cos d\theta \leq L(1, 2, 3, 4)$ for some θ , then that would complete the evaluation of $\lambda(4)$. Perhaps it is possible to reduce each M_j to a finite collection of subsets of \mathbb{N}'_4 that have 2 degrees of freedom.

6. Bounds on $\mu(5)$

It was observed in [6] that

$$M(0, 1, 2, 6, 9) = \min_{|z|=1} |1 + z + z^2 + z^6 + z^9| = 1$$

and it is suspected that $\mu(5) = 1$, although this appears to be difficult to prove. In this section, we give a short elementary argument showing that $\mu(5) \leq \sqrt{3} \approx 1.732$, and a longer case analysis showing that $\mu(5) \leq 1 + \pi/5 \approx 1.628$. More generally, we will show that for any positive integer m , the problem of showing $\mu(5) \leq 1 + \pi/m$ can be reduced to checking a finite number of cases. In particular, we will sketch a proof that $\mu(5) \leq 1 + \pi/6 \approx 1.524$.

To show $\mu(5) \leq K$, we must show that for all of the infinitely many $(0, a, b, c, d)$ in \mathbb{N}_5'' , we have $|1 + z^a + z^b + z^c + z^d| \leq K$ for some $|z| = 1$.

Let $(0, a, b, c, d) \in \mathbb{N}_5''$. To show $|1 + z^a + z^b + z^c + z^d| \leq \sqrt{3}$ for some $|z| = 1$, define $S = \{\theta \in \mathbb{T} \mid d\theta = \pi\}$, and let $z = e^{i\theta}$. Observe that we have

$$\begin{aligned} |z^a + z^b + z^c|^2 &= (z^a + z^b + z^c)(z^{-a} + z^{-b} + z^{-c}) \\ &= 3 + (z^{b-a} + z^{a-b}) + (z^{c-a} + z^{a-c}) + (z^{c-b} + z^{b-c}) \\ &= 3 + \cos(b - a)\theta + \cos(c - a)\theta + \cos(c - b)\theta. \end{aligned}$$

Now note that $b - a, c - a, c - b$ are positive integers less than d , so they are not multiples of d . It follows that the average of $|z^a + z^b + z^c|^2$ over S is 3. Therefore at least one $\theta \in S$ satisfies $|z^a + z^b + z^c|^2 \leq 3$ and hence $|1 + z^a + z^b + z^c + z^d| = |z^a + z^b + z^c| \leq \sqrt{3}$.

To get better bounds on $\mu(5)$, we will use some straightforward lemmas similar to those in Section 3.

Lemma 6.1. *If θ satisfies $|\theta - \pi| \leq \delta$, then $|1 + e^{i\theta}| \leq \delta$.*

Lemma 6.2. *Let k, ℓ, m be distinct positive integers with $\ell < m$, and let $g = \gcd(k, m - \ell)$. We then have*

$$|1 + z^k + z^\ell + z^m| \leq \frac{\pi g}{k}$$

for some z on the unit circle.

Proof. Define the sets

$$\begin{aligned} S_1 &= \{\theta \in \mathbb{T} \mid k\theta = \pi\}, \\ S_2 &= \{\theta \in \mathbb{T} \mid (m - \ell)\theta = \pi\}, \end{aligned}$$

which are equispaced sets of order k and $m - \ell$ respectively. By Lemma 3.1, there exist $\theta_1 \in S_1$ and $\theta_2 \in S_2$ such that $|\theta_1 - \theta_2| \leq \frac{\pi g}{k(m-\ell)}$, and hence

$$|(m - \ell)\theta_1 - \pi| = |(m - \ell)\theta_1 - (m - \ell)\theta_2| \leq \frac{\pi g}{k}.$$

Then, if $z = e^{i\theta_1}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} |1 + z^k + z^\ell + z^m| &= |1 + z^k + z^\ell(1 + z^{m-\ell})| = |1 + e^{ik\theta_1} + z^\ell(1 + z^{m-\ell})| \\ &= |1 - 1 + z^\ell(1 + z^{m-\ell})| = |z^\ell(1 + z^{m-\ell})| = |1 + z^{m-\ell}| \end{aligned}$$

which, by Lemma 6.1, is at most $\pi g/k$. □

Now to prove $\mu(5) \leq 1 + \pi/5$, let $(0, a, b, c, d) \in \mathbb{N}'_5$, and define $\alpha(z) = 1 + z^a + z^b + z^c + z^d$. We must show that

$$|\alpha(z)| \leq 1 + \frac{\pi}{5}$$

for some z on the unit circle. From the definition of \mathbb{N}'_5 , we have not only $0 < a < b < c < d$, but also $c \geq d - a$, which implies $c > d - b$. We thus have the following inequalities, where both sides are positive integers:

$$\begin{aligned} d &> b - a \\ d &> c - b \\ d &> c - a \\ c &> b - a \\ c &> d - b \\ c &\geq d - a \end{aligned}$$

We now define

$$\begin{aligned} g_1 &= \gcd(d, b - a) && \text{so } g_1 \leq b - a < d \\ g_2 &= \gcd(d, c - b) && \text{so } g_2 \leq c - b < d \\ g_3 &= \gcd(d, c - a) && \text{so } g_3 \leq c - a < d \\ g_4 &= \gcd(c, b - a) && \text{so } g_4 \leq b - a < c \\ g_5 &= \gcd(c, d - b) && \text{so } g_5 \leq d - b < c \\ g_6 &= \gcd(c, d - a) && \text{so } g_6 \leq d - a \leq c. \end{aligned}$$

Applying Lemma 6.2 to the case $(k, \ell, m) = (d, a, b)$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} |\alpha(z)| &\leq |z^c| + |1 + z^d + z^a + z^b| \\ &= 1 + |1 + z^d + z^a + z^b| \leq 1 + \frac{\pi g_1}{d} \quad \text{for some } |z| = 1. \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, applying Lemma 6.2 to each of the cases

$$\begin{aligned} (k, \ell, m) &= (d, b, c) \\ (k, \ell, m) &= (d, a, c) \\ (k, \ell, m) &= (c, a, b) \\ (k, \ell, m) &= (c, b, d) \\ (k, \ell, m) &= (c, a, d), \end{aligned}$$

we can conclude that we have

$$\begin{aligned} |\alpha(z)| &\leq 1 + \frac{\pi g_2}{d} && \text{for some } |z| = 1 \\ |\alpha(z)| &\leq 1 + \frac{\pi g_3}{d} && \text{for some } |z| = 1 \\ |\alpha(z)| &\leq 1 + \frac{\pi g_4}{c} && \text{for some } |z| = 1 \\ |\alpha(z)| &\leq 1 + \frac{\pi g_5}{c} && \text{for some } |z| = 1 \\ |\alpha(z)| &\leq 1 + \frac{\pi g_6}{c} && \text{for some } |z| = 1. \end{aligned}$$

If any of the six numbers

$$\frac{g_1}{d}, \frac{g_2}{d}, \frac{g_3}{d}, \frac{g_4}{c}, \frac{g_5}{c}, \frac{g_6}{c} \tag{1}$$

is less than or equal to $1/5$, we are done. So for the remainder of the proof, we assume each of those six numbers is greater than $1/5$.

Note that d and $b - a$ are integer multiples of g_1 , with $d > b - a$. The condition $g_1/d > 1/5$ is equivalent to $d < 5g_1$, which implies that $d \in \{2g_1, 3g_1, 4g_1\}$. Then since $b - a$ is an integer multiple of g_1 smaller than d , one of the following must be true:

$$\begin{aligned} d = 2g_1 \text{ and } b - a = g_1 &\implies \frac{1}{2}d = b - a \\ d = 3g_1 \text{ and } b - a = g_1 &\implies \frac{1}{3}d = b - a \\ d = 3g_1 \text{ and } b - a = 2g_1 &\implies \frac{2}{3}d = b - a \\ d = 4g_1 \text{ and } b - a = g_1 &\implies \frac{1}{4}d = b - a \\ d = 4g_1 \text{ and } b - a = 3g_1 &\implies \frac{3}{4}d = b - a \end{aligned}$$

So we have $rd = b - a$, where

$$r \in \left\{ \frac{1}{4}, \frac{1}{3}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{2}{3}, \frac{3}{4} \right\}.$$

We will now apply similar reasoning to the other five expressions in (1). Note that the following hold:

- d and $c - b$ are integer multiples of g_2 with $d > c - b$, and $d < 5g_2$
- d and $c - a$ are integer multiples of g_3 with $d > c - a$, and $d < 5g_3$
- c and $b - a$ are integer multiples of g_4 with $c > b - a$, and $c < 5g_4$
- c and $d - b$ are integer multiples of g_5 with $c > d - b$, and $c < 5g_5$
- c and $d - a$ are integer multiples of g_6 with $c \geq d - a$, and $c < 5g_6$.

Notice the slight difference in the last line. This means that our list of possibilities for c and $d - a$ will include $c = d - a = g_6$.

Using similar reasoning as before, we can conclude:

$$\begin{aligned} rd &= b - a, \text{ where } r \in \left\{ \frac{1}{4}, \frac{1}{3}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{2}{3}, \frac{3}{4} \right\} \\ sd &= c - b, \text{ where } s \in \left\{ \frac{1}{4}, \frac{1}{3}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{2}{3}, \frac{3}{4} \right\} \\ td &= c - a, \text{ where } t \in \left\{ \frac{1}{4}, \frac{1}{3}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{2}{3}, \frac{3}{4} \right\} \\ uc &= b - a, \text{ where } u \in \left\{ \frac{1}{4}, \frac{1}{3}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{2}{3}, \frac{3}{4} \right\} \\ vc &= d - b, \text{ where } v \in \left\{ \frac{1}{4}, \frac{1}{3}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{2}{3}, \frac{3}{4} \right\} \\ wc &= d - a, \text{ where } w \in \left\{ \frac{1}{4}, \frac{1}{3}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{2}{3}, \frac{3}{4}, 1 \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

Thus there are finitely many possibilities for r, s, t, u, v, w . Notice that this remains true if we change our goal from showing $\mu(5) \leq 1 + \pi/5$ to showing $\mu(5) \leq 1 + \pi/m$. In that case, the possible values for r, s, t, u, v, w are fractions between 0 and 1 whose denominators are less than m .

We claim that for each of the finitely many possible triples r, s, u , there is at most one element of \mathbb{N}'_5 satisfying the three conditions

$$\begin{aligned} rd &= b - a \\ sd &= c - b \\ uc &= b - a. \end{aligned}$$

To verify this claim, we write these conditions as

$$\begin{aligned} 1a - 1b + 0c + rd &= 0 \\ 0a + 1b - 1c + sd &= 0 \\ 1a - 1b + uc + 0d &= 0, \end{aligned}$$

which we temporarily regard as a system of equations in *rational* unknowns a, b, c, d .

Writing as a matrix and row-reducing, we have

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 & 0 & r \\ 0 & 1 & -1 & s \\ 1 & -1 & u & 0 \end{bmatrix} \rightarrow \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 & 0 & r \\ 0 & 1 & -1 & s \\ 0 & 0 & u & -r \end{bmatrix} \rightarrow \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 & 0 & r \\ 0 & 1 & -1 & s \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & -\frac{r}{u} \end{bmatrix}.$$

Note that u is always nonzero. Continuing, we have

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 & 0 & r \\ 0 & 1 & -1 & s \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & -\frac{r}{u} \end{bmatrix} \rightarrow \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 & 0 & r \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & s - \frac{r}{u} \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & -\frac{r}{u} \end{bmatrix} \rightarrow \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & r + s - \frac{r}{u} \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & s - \frac{r}{u} \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & -\frac{r}{u} \end{bmatrix}.$$

It follows that the system has an infinite one-parameter family of *rational* solutions, given by

$$\begin{aligned} a &= \left(\frac{r}{u} - r - s\right)q \\ b &= \left(\frac{r}{u} - s\right)q \\ c &= \left(\frac{r}{u}\right)q \\ d &= q, \end{aligned}$$

where q can be any rational number. In other words, the rational solutions (a, b, c, d) are precisely the rational multiples of the 4-tuple

$$\left(\frac{r}{u} - r - s, \frac{r}{u} - s, \frac{r}{u}, 1\right).$$

However, at most one rational multiple of a given rational 4-tuple can consist of relatively prime nonnegative integers. That is, there is at most one possible $(0, a, b, c, d) \in \mathbb{N}_5'$ for each choice of r, s, u .

For the specific case of showing $\mu(5) \leq 1 + \pi/5$, it is possible to enumerate all the possibilities by hand. Recall that we have the restrictions

$$\begin{aligned} rd &= b - a, \text{ where } r \in \left\{\frac{1}{4}, \frac{1}{3}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{2}{3}, \frac{3}{4}\right\} \\ sd &= c - b, \text{ where } s \in \left\{\frac{1}{4}, \frac{1}{3}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{2}{3}, \frac{3}{4}\right\} \\ td &= c - a, \text{ where } t \in \left\{\frac{1}{4}, \frac{1}{3}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{2}{3}, \frac{3}{4}\right\} \\ uc &= b - a, \text{ where } u \in \left\{\frac{1}{4}, \frac{1}{3}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{2}{3}, \frac{3}{4}\right\} \\ vc &= d - b, \text{ where } v \in \left\{\frac{1}{4}, \frac{1}{3}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{2}{3}, \frac{3}{4}\right\} \\ wc &= d - a, \text{ where } w \in \left\{\frac{1}{4}, \frac{1}{3}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{2}{3}, \frac{3}{4}, 1\right\}. \end{aligned}$$

Notice that

$$(r + s)d = rd + sd = (b - a) + (c - b) = c - a = td$$

r	s	t
1/4	1/4	1/2
1/4	1/2	3/4
1/3	1/3	2/3
1/2	1/4	3/4

Table 2: Permissible values of r, s, t

u	v	w
1/4	1/4	1/2
1/4	1/2	3/4
1/4	3/4	1
1/3	1/3	2/3
1/3	2/3	1
1/2	1/4	3/4
1/2	1/2	1
2/3	1/3	1
3/4	1/4	1

Table 3: Permissible values of u, v, w

so $r + s = t$, and also notice that

$$(u + v)c = uc + vc = (b - a) + (d - b) = d - a = wc$$

so $u + v = w$. The only permissible values of r, s, t that satisfy this are shown in Table 2, and the only permissible values of u, v, w that satisfy this are shown in Table 3. Next, notice that we have $rd = b - a = uc$, which together with $c < d$ implies that $u > r$. Also notice that we have

$$sd = c - b \text{ implies } b = c - sd$$

$$vc = d - b \text{ implies } b = d - vc$$

$$c - sd = d - vc \text{ implies } c + vc = d + sd \text{ implies } (1 + v)c = (1 + s)d,$$

which together with $c < d$ implies $1 + v > 1 + s$, so $v > s$. The only permissible values of r, s, u, v satisfying both $u > r$ and $v > s$ are shown in Table 4. We now use the conditions $rd = uc$ and $(1 + v)c = (1 + s)d$ to conclude

$$\frac{r}{u} = \frac{c}{d} = \frac{1 + s}{1 + v}, \text{ implying } r(1 + v) = u(1 + s)$$

which only some of our possible values of r, s, u, v will satisfy. We see in Table 5 that only one of our possibilities satisfies $r(1 + v) = u(1 + s)$. We conclude that $(r, s, u, v) = (\frac{1}{4}, \frac{1}{4}, \frac{1}{3}, \frac{2}{3})$. We then have

$$\left(\frac{r}{u} - r - s, \frac{r}{u} - s, \frac{r}{u}, 1\right) = \left(\frac{1}{4}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{3}{4}, 1\right),$$

r	s	u	v
1/4	1/4	1/3	1/3
1/4	1/4	1/3	2/3
1/4	1/4	1/2	1/2
1/4	1/4	2/3	1/3
1/4	1/2	1/3	2/3
1/3	1/3	1/2	1/2
1/2	1/4	2/3	1/3

Table 4: Permissible values of r, s, u, v satisfying $u > r$ and $v > s$

r	s	u	v	$1 + s$	$1 + v$	$r(1 + v)$	$u(1 + s)$
1/4	1/4	1/3	1/3	5/4	4/3	1/3	5/12
1/4	1/4	1/3	2/3	5/4	5/3	5/12	5/12
1/4	1/4	1/2	1/2	5/4	3/2	3/8	5/8
1/4	1/4	2/3	1/3	5/4	4/3	1/3	5/6
1/4	1/2	1/3	2/3	3/2	5/3	5/12	1/2
1/3	1/3	1/2	1/2	4/3	3/2	1/2	2/3
1/2	1/4	2/3	1/3	5/4	4/3	2/3	5/6

Table 5: Checking whether $r(1 + v) = u(1 + s)$

implying $(a, b, c, d) = (1, 2, 3, 4)$. But the polynomial $f(z) = 1 + z + z^2 + z^3 + z^4$ certainly satisfies $|f(z)| \leq 1 + \pi/5$ for some $|z| = 1$, because it has zeros at the nontrivial fifth roots of unity. This completes the proof that $\mu(5) \leq 1 + \pi/5$.

The above argument can be modified to show that $\mu(5) \leq 1 + \pi/m$ for some other positive integers m , but doing so by hand is cumbersome and computer assistance is helpful. We will give a rough outline of an argument that $\mu(5) \leq 1 + \pi/6$.

This time, the argument involves finding r, s, t, u, v, w that satisfy

$$\begin{aligned}
 rd &= b - a \\
 sd &= c - b \\
 td &= c - a \\
 uc &= b - a \\
 vc &= d - b \\
 wc &= d - a,
 \end{aligned}$$

where $0 < r, s, t, u, v < 1$, $0 < w \leq 1$, and r, s, t, u, v, w are fractions with denominators strictly less than 6. They must further satisfy

$$r + s = t, \quad u + v = w, \quad r < u, \quad s < v, \quad r(1 + v) = u(1 + s).$$

A finite search (aided by computer) reveals that the only eligible values of r, s, u, v

r	s	u	v	$1 + s$	$1 + v$
1/3	1/3	2/5	3/5	4/3	8/5
1/4	1/4	1/3	2/3	5/4	5/3
1/5	1/5	1/4	1/2	6/5	3/2
1/5	2/5	1/4	3/4	7/5	7/4
2/5	1/5	1/2	1/2	6/5	3/2
3/5	1/5	2/3	1/3	6/5	4/3

Table 6: Eligible r, s, u, v with denominators less than 6

$\frac{r}{u} - r - s$	$\frac{r}{u} - s$	$\frac{r}{u}$	(a, b, c, d)
1/6	3/6	5/6	(1, 3, 5, 6)
1/4	2/4	3/4	(1, 2, 3, 4)
2/5	3/5	4/5	(2, 3, 4, 5)
1/5	2/5	4/5	(1, 2, 4, 5)
1/5	3/5	4/5	(1, 3, 4, 5)
1/10	7/10	9/10	(1, 7, 9, 10)

Table 7: Eligible 4-tuples for verifying $\mu(5) \leq 1 + \pi/6$

are those shown in Table 6. (The values of $1 + s$ and $1 + v$ are included for convenience.) As before, each eligible (r, s, u, v) gives us a 4-tuple

$$\left(\frac{r}{u} - r - s, \frac{r}{u} - s, \frac{r}{u}, 1\right)$$

of which precisely one integer multiple is an eligible (a, b, c, d) . This gives us six possibilities, shown in Table 7. One can verify that for each of these six possibilities for (a, b, c, d) , we have

$$|1 + z^a + z^b + z^c + z^d| \leq 1 + \pi/6$$

for some $|z| = 1$. This completes the sketch of the proof that $\mu(5) \leq 1 + \pi/6$.

In conclusion, note that the contributions of Campbell et al. and Goddard appeared gradually. The results in this paper can be regarded as extensions of that work. It appears that evaluating $\lambda(n)$ or $\mu(n)$ in finitely many steps is a genuinely subtle problem.

References

- [1] D.W. Boyd, Large Newman polynomials, in *Diophantine Analysis (Kensington, 1985)*, 159–170, London Math. Soc. Lecture Note Ser., 109, Cambridge Univ. Press, Cambridge, 1986.
- [2] D.M. Campbell, H.R.P. Ferguson and R.W. Forcade, Newman polynomials on $|z| = 1$, *Indiana Univ. Math. J.* **32** (1983), 517–525.

- [3] S. Chowla, The Riemann zeta and allied functions, *Bull. Amer. Math. Soc.* **58** (1952), 287–305.
- [4] S. Chowla, Some applications of a method of A. Selberg, *J. Reine Angew. Math.* **217** (1965), 128–132.
- [5] P.J. Cohen, On a conjecture of Littlewood and idempotent measures, *Amer. J. Math.* **82** (1960), 191–212.
- [6] B. Goddard, Finite exponential series and Newman polynomials, *Proc. Amer. Math. Soc.* **116** (1992), 313–320.
- [7] I. Mercer, Newman polynomials not vanishing on the unit circle, *Integers* **12** (2012), A67, 7 pp.
- [8] I.Z. Ruzsa, Negative values of cosine sums, *Acta Arith.* **111** (2004), 179–186.
- [9] M. Uchiyama (née Katayama) and S. Uchiyama, On the cosine problem, *Proc. Japan Acad.* **36** (1960), 475–479.